

Influence of Social Media Use, Age and Gender on Moral Behaviour of Teenage Undergraduates in Imo State.

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Abstract: This cross-sectional survey examines how social media influences the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates in three universities in Imo State: Federal University of Technology, Owerri (FUTO), Imo State University, Owerri (IMSU), and University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo (UAES). A total of 405 participants (206 males and 199 females, aged 17-19, mean age 18.87) were randomly selected. The study utilized the Social Networking Usage Questionnaire (SNUQ) by Gupta and Bashir (2018) to assess social media engagement, Omoluabi's (1999) Ethical-Moral Self Inventory (EMSI) to evaluate moral behavior, and self-constructed demographic questions. One-Way ANOVA, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypotheses of the study using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21). Among the three tested hypotheses, one was rejected while two were accepted. Findings indicate a significant increase in use of social media among teenage undergraduates in Imo State, with moral deterioration linked to social media engagement irrespective of age and gender. The study underscores the necessity for policy interventions, including incorporating use of social media guidelines in educational curricula to foster responsible digital consumption.

Keywords: *Use of Social Media, Teenagers, Moral Behaviour, Gender, Age.*

Introduction

Social Media is a huge part of most teenagers' daily life. Research suggests that prolonged exposure to violent media can lead to behavioral changes in children (Guerrero *et al.*, 2019), similar to the effects of excessive social media use. The

increasing reliance on digital platforms has significantly altered communication patterns, personal relationships, and education. Teenagers, particularly undergraduate students, are key demographic, navigating a

critical stage of academic and personal development.

Social media encompasses various online interactive platforms that facilitate content exchange, including Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok (Naslund, 2016). The proliferation of social has led to the introduction of new platforms and the evolution or disappearance of older ones. Popular social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, You Tube, Pinterest, Snapchat, and TikTok provide environments for communication, assertiveness, and information sharing.

Social media has significantly contributed to the creation and dissemination of information; encouraging change and swell chances for individuals in creating and sharing content by the users (Chukwuere, 2021; Adem and Derya, 2022). Features such as shares, hashtags, mentions, retweets, and likes have facilitated the viral spread of content (James, 2020). While social media offers numerous advantages, such as increased access to information and enhanced connectivity, it also presents challenges and risks, particularly concerning moral behaviour and development. Researchers have noted that social media can promote social distancing, fear, anxiety, and the manipulation of public opinion (James, 2020).

In Nigeria, changes in social media have significantly impacted business operations, particularly among unemployed youths who leverage e-commerce opportunities (Ugochukwu, 2022). However, it has also raised moral concerns among teenagers, who use these platforms for diverse purposes, including education and social interactions.

Understanding how social media influences demographics such as gender and age is crucial for targeted policies and interventions. Adolescence, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2024) as ages 10–19, is a critical stage for emotional, mental, social and health development. Adem and Derya, (2022) attribute this stage to often involves exploring and engaging in behaviour related with social media. Addiction of social media is classified as a behavioral disorder due to the compulsion to engage in social media apps and it is detrimental to the day-to-day tasks (Cheng, Ebrahimi, and Luk, 2022). The cravings for social media interactions have been linked to dopamine, a neurotransmitter associated with mood, attention, motivation and memory.

The American Tweens and Teens study identified increased social media use during the COVID-19 pandemic, with adolescents' daily screen time rising from 7:22 to 8:39 hours and younger adolescents (Tweens)

from 4:44 to 5:33 hours, with Tik Tok being the most used app (Common Sense Census, 2021). Despite restrictions on account creation for minors, many teenagers bypass these limitations, gaining access to contents for adults. As noted by Uzuegbunam, (2020), 63.7 percent of 14-to-18-years old in Nigeria have mobile phones, highlighting the growing number of teenagers accessing internet apps. UNICEF (2017) observed that one-third of internet users are underage, with those aged 15 to 25 being the highest percentage of online users. Researchers have linked excessive social media use to moral decline poor academic performance, and increased social media addiction (Otubue and Oji, 2024; Oloyede and Oloyede, 2022).

Morality refers to a set of standards that guide individuals to coexist harmoniously in groups, distinguishing right from wrong (Morin, 2024). The negative consequences of social media include sexual promiscuity, cybercrime, indecent clothing, impatience, cyber trolling, sexual harassment, internet addiction, and exposure to indecent content. Conversely, some researchers argue that social media benefits teenagers by promoting social interaction, enhancing creativity, and lowering communication barriers (Chukwuere, 2021; Oloyede and Oloyede, 2022).

Gender, a social construct, influences use of social media and interactions, defining societal expectations and values for men and women (United Nations Statistics, 2020). This research focuses on biological males and females using social media to facilitate relationships and interactions, particularly, among teenagers in Nigeria universities. The study examines how the use of social media affects moral behaviour, gender and age among undergraduate teenagers in three universities in Imo State, Nigeria: the Federal University of Technology Owerri (FUTO), Imo State University Owerri (IMSU), and the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES) Umuagwo. This research aims to explore the psychological disorders and moral challenges associated with use of social media among this demographic.

Statement of the Problem

The high significant use of smart gadgets and the active presence on the internet apps is a growing concern and a frequent subject of research. The lack of a systematic approach to regulating teenagers' social media use has resulted in various cybercrimes such as hacking, identity theft, cyber harassment, pornography, spamming, ATM spoofing, phishing, piracy and prostitution (Omodunbi, Odiase, *et al.*, 2016). Other crimes, including ritualism, substance abuse and the pursuit of quick

wealth, have also been linked to social media (Dango, 2021). Due to insufficient regulation, nations worldwide, including Nigeria, are advocating for stricter controls on social media activities.

There is an urgent need to protect young people, especially teenagers, from harmful online content as immorality and neglect of education among teenagers increase. The alarming rise in interest among Nigerian boys and girls in gaining wealth and displaying affluence through cybercrime and ritual killings is particularly troubling. Additionally, female teenagers, driven by the desire to appear fashionable and gain fame, are engaging in cyber prostitution, often resulting in abuse and even death, linked to social media influences.

Uncontrolled use of social media by youths, especially teenagers, has negatively affected both genders, leading to a lack of motivation to live responsibly and a deeper entrenchment in the virtual world. These issues underscore the importance of this research, which aims to determine influence of social media on the moral behaviour, gender and age of teenage undergraduates in Imo State.

Objectives of the Study

The major aim of this research is targeted on examining the influence social media, age and gender has on the moral behaviour of

the teenage undergraduates' in specified universities in Imo State.

Specific objectives are:

1. To explore whether use of social media will significantly predicts the moral behaviour of teenage undergraduates.
2. To assess whether the teenage undergraduates' age will significantly predicts the moral behaviour.
3. To identify whether male and female undergraduates will significantly differ on their moral behaviour.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Social Cognition

Bandura's (1989) theory of social cognition is of the view that individuals who observe performing models, consequentially, follow the patterns as they recall the order of the behaviours and apply the information in building the next behaviours. Apparently, users of social apps internalize as well as reproduce the observed behaviors. Social media technology has fundamentally altered life communication processes as well as different aspects of social interaction. Many social media users, in their attempt to imitate influencers, often influence themselves. This phenomenon occurs because the content they create and the interactions they generate – such as shares,

repost, likes, and follows- drive traffic to their accounts, increasing their visibility and activity ratings, which can lead to fame.

Moreover, the intermittent rewards provided by these apps, such as monetary compensation, spur users to increase their engagement to monetize their accounts. This pursuit of imitating influencers and keeping up with fashion trends and ideas can easily lead users to compromise their ethics and social behaviours. The theory of social cognition illustrates the connection between traditional and current media use and individual behaviours. Research has indicated that the drive to imitate and the resulting social control are fundamental aspects of individual goal-oriented behaviour (Stefanone, Yue, and Toh, 2018).

Theory of Planned Behavior and Norms (TPB)

Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1991) posits that humans are naturally rational and respond to stimuli based on specific aspects of behavioural control. The theory highlights social norms, subjective norms, attitudes, perceived power, behavioural intentions and perceived behavioural control are key factors influencing decision-making. Unlike the Social Cognitive Theory, the Theory of Planned Behaviour suggests that behavioural performance depends on both behavioural control and intentions. Individuals' targeted behaviours are more

likely to develop when they are motivated to act. As a result, the probability involving the specific behaviour is high as their intents strengthen (McLaughlin and Stevens, 2015).

In the context of media apps, the subscribers are comfortably controlled as their decision-making process is flawed. This can impact their morality, as they are motivated to emulate influencers, which can distort their cognition and alter their overall behavioural patterns.

Literature Review

Teenagers' Use of Social Media and Moral Behaviour

Teens' regular exposure to technological gadgets and apps exposes them to various threatening materials shared on social media, many are fake or unfounded. They are particularly vulnerable to believing and trying out things they see, hear, and read due to issues of character control during their maturation stage. Self-regulation, which is crucial for activity execution and cognition in the prefrontal cortex, typically matures by the age of 25. This self-regulation helps control emotions, motivation, and behaviour, aiding in navigating environmental challenges.

A Study by Data Reportal (2024), reveals that about 16.2% of people in Nigeria use social media at the beginning of 2024, excluding certain individuals who were not

counted for specific reasons. Contrastingly, data from top social media platforms before 2024 indicates that 32.0% of the adult population, approximately 36.70 million Nigerians aged 18 and above, used social media. Additionally, before 2024, 35.7% of Nigerians used at least one social media app.

Teenagers' Use of Social Media and Moral Behaviour

Ismail (2023) study evaluated the moral behaviour of female students in a Baghdad high school in relation to their social media usage. Using a quantitative method of data collection, the results indicated that 73.9% of the participants scored low on the moral test, showing a significant correlation between social media use and moral behaviour at the 0.00 level. The study emphasized the need to raise awareness about the negative influence of social media on adolescents' moral development.

There is a clear distinction between the school and home environment, with many teenagers recognizing the differences in moral development contexts. Modern families often delegate the responsibility of parenting to educational institutions and care centers, rather than monitoring the activities of their youths themselves (Tan and Yasin, 2020). To combat immorality, Nigerian society has historically installed moral values through initiatives like the War Against Indiscipline (WAI) and continues to

do with agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the National Orientation Agency (NOA), which educate the public and debunk behaviours that tarnish the country's image (Adedigba and Wahab, 2015).

Premium Times News (March, 2022) covered the story of four males that three were teenagers in Ogun State, Nigeria, who were detained for reportedly beheading and burning the head of a female teenager for money ritual purposes. On interrogation, they disclosed that they obtained the ritual directions from a social media app known as Facebook. Also, Punch Metro (April, 2022) reported on a viral video involving teenage students from Chrisland Schools Abuja under the age of 15 being caught engaging in sexual intercourse while filming themselves. Findings subsequently showed that one of the girls in the viral video has been quite active on TikTok, popular social medium platform, where she routinely uploads sexy dance movements for her over twelve thousand followers.

The descriptive research study of Otubue and Oji (2024) examines how social media affects morality and group norms of secondary school students in delta state Nigeria. Using multi-stage sampling technique and selecting about 250 respondents, data collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using

frequency count and percentage observed high use of social media among the participants. It states that students use all social media apps for sexual compliments from friends and admirers. Also, sexual exposures on social media significantly influence social values and group norms among others. It recommends serious control by parents on the use especially postings regarding to sexual contents be.

Oloyede and Oloyede (2022) study on influence of social media on morality and how religion is mediating in Nigeria context identifies immorality as major antisocial behaviour as a part of the disadvantages of social media. Using survey research method of literature reviews and observations, it observes cyberbullying, pornography, lesbianism, homosexuals, bullying remarks that result in violence are all linked to inappropriate use of media apps. These threaten the educational achievement as well as general welfare of Nigerian youths. It concludes that social media evidently is a wide promoter of antics of morality and moral deterioration in the society.

Age and Moral Behaviour

Hertz and Krettenauer (2016) meta-analysis study demonstrated how age-related differences of adults can affect morality. Based on 111 studies from diverse faculty of academics that includes developmental

psychology, sociology, business, marketing, sports science and education, 252 population, age ranged from 14 to 65 years of 148 female, and mean age of 33.5 years and standard deviation of 16.9, result after self- assessment questionnaire revealed a total reduction in increase of context differentiation with age showing a negative linear regression among others.

Lu and Fung (2019) research negatively associated age with moral behaviour as it examines age-related factors in cognitive and affective specifics of morality towards moral punishment. Engaging 120 participants aged twenty-two to seventy-five selected within Mturk town had test of moral transgressions cases that assessed their moral conviction, wrongness judgement, moral punishment and emotional experience. Outcomes showed varying patterns among age along with assessment on cognition and emotion. Older adults believe that higher immoral behaviours are more wrong than younger adults in cognition to their moral conviction but have low negative emotions, indicating they have minimal arousal by immoral behaviours.

Ismail (2023) showed that adolescents' high school students of Bagdad have more ethical issues as regards to use of social media and morality. The study used quantitative method of data collection and the outcome had adolescents of 15 to 17 years; N= 343,

82.9% higher than younger adults of 18 to 20 years; N=61, 97.6%. The all had low score by the moral assessment and 0.00 level correlations were observed.

Gender and Moral Behaviour

Data Reportal (2024), states that the greater numbers of male (58.3%) use media than the female (41.7%) counterparts. However, the females spend much time daily in surfing all through social media apps than the males. There is recognition of the presence of both gender in use of social media as Muhammed-Lawal and Salahu-Deen (2021) descriptive study had 365 participants of 185 male; 50.7% and 180 female; 49.3% being secondary school students in western Nigeria were examined with self-constructed questionnaire. Using T-test analysis the result showed that there is no significant difference between gender and moral behaviour of the students as (P-value = 0.375 > α at 0.005).

Hypotheses

Use of social media will not significantly predict the moral behaviour of the teenage undergraduates.

The teenage undergraduates' age will not significantly predict moral behaviour.

Male and female undergraduates will not significantly differ on their moral behaviour.

Methodology

This study was a cross sectional design survey. The participants engaged were 405 made up of 199 females and 206 males 'teenagers selected from three universities in Imo State via clustered sampling. Stratified random sampling was applied to select participants from diverse clusters. Their age brackets were 17-19 years old and mean age of 18 years.

Three instruments were employed for the data collection and they were self-constructed questionnaire of social demographic that examined the socio-demographic of the respondents. This includes age, gender, school, matriculation numbers, and level. Social Networking Usage Questionnaires (SNUQ) was the second questionnaire administered to the respondents developed by Gupta and Bashir (2018). This instrument was produced for the assessment of social network activities or level someone uses the apps. It consists of 19 questions in 4 dimensions and response method of 5-point Likert scale. Its reliability statistics is on Cronbach's alpha, at 83 as convergent validity Pearson's coefficient correlation. The levels of positive significant had correlations of SNUQ. Calculated scores interrelationship of the measurements are within .593 to .894, making SNUG concurrently valid (Scholte, Engels, et al, 2007). Responding scores are

as follows: Never = 1, Rarely = 2, Sometimes = 3, Often = 4, Always = 5. The internal consistency was measured using Cronbach's alpha as reliability approved by Gliem and Gliem, (2003). The reliability coefficient alpha basically lays with-in 0 and 1 as the interpretation rating point from 0.80 Cronbach's alpha (George and Mallery, 2003). Apparently, Gupta and Bashir (2018) pinned SNUQ's Cronbach alpha .83, showing the good internal consistent. SNUQ is scored directly as increased scores show increased use of social media as decreased scores shows decreased use of social media use. The pilot study was done in Nigeria by Ekemam (2014), confirmed the reliability and validity with 80 respondents drawn from Imo Secondary School using convenient sampling method. About 49 females and 21 males aged within 12 years and 19 years with mean age of 14.84 and 1.725 for standard deviation. For this study, SNUQ norm is .88 and 62.94 reliability Cronbach rate.

Another questionnaire used is Ethical Moral Self-Inventory (EMSI) by Omoluabi (1999). It is a 28-item scale designed to measure individual's degree of morality, ethical standards, religiosity, and super-ego functioning in Nigeria. The EMSI contains 10 self-criticism and 18 moral-ethical self-assessment items adopted from the Tennessee Self-Concept Scale (TSCS) by

Fitts (1965). EMSI was developed at the backdrop of increasing significant morality assumption in Nigeria clinical and social research. Morality as conceptualized by the scale is the tendency by an individual to adopt the principle of fairness, integrity, and justice in guiding his or her behaviour in social interactions. The ethico-morality covers more ground than adopting the principle of right and wrong to evaluate social situations. Its responses rating include 1 = Completely False, 2 = Mostly False, 3 = Partly False and Partly True, 4 = Mostly True, and 5 = Completely True. The self-criticism scale usually for clinical purposes is the validity scale of the TSCS. EMSI has items 1,2,6,11,12,16,21,22,and 25 as direct scoring and 3,7,8,13,17,18,28,23,26,and 27 as reverse scoring, while 4,5,9,10,14,15,19,20,24 and 28 directly score as self-criticism scale. The final score is gotten after the total sum of the direct and reverse scores. Fitts (1965) established the original psychometric properties for American samples while Ezeilo (1982, 1983) and Olukoya (1998), provided the Nigerian sample properties as follow: male teenagers 61.90, females 60.20; male adolescents 63.70, female 64.10 and adults 63.96 for both gender while SCS for both male and female is 32.11. The test-retest reliability coefficients obtained for the full TSCS test of which EMSI is a subscale are .92 by Fitts (1965) and .74 Ezeilo (1982). Olukoya

(1998) obtained a concurrent validity coefficient to -.015 by correlating EMSI with the Index of Self-Esteem (Hudson, 1982). Nigerian teenage norms were the basis for interpreting the scores and scores higher than the norms indicate adequate or high ethical and moral behaviour while scores lower than the norms indicate poor or inadequate ethical and moral behaviour.

The instruments were distributed to the respondents from the sampled schools through the help of the research assistant that asked for their consent before letting them participate in the study and preceded in data collection. It took average of 15-30

minutes to finish each questionnaires as ethical conducts of consent approval and confidentiality were duly observed.

SPSS (IBM Corp, 2020) was used in analyzing collated data; Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis tested number 1 and number 2 hypotheses. Wubante (2020) supported this as correlation enables researchers in being predictive. Number 3 hypothesis was tested using One-Way ANOVA, as it aids assessing in-between group variables. The researchers interpreted and discussed the results accordingly.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Moral Behaviour, Use of Social Media and Age Correlation among Undergraduate Teenagers.

S/N	Variables	SD	M	1	2	3	4
1	Moral Behaviour	59.69	7.37	.060	1		
2	Use of Social Media	75.12	7.65	-.186***	-.214***	1	
3	Age	18.84	5.02	-.045	-.025	-.010	1

Note: SD – Standard deviation, M - Mean

From the above table, the moral behaviour mean score is 59.69 which is lower than the norm of the moral behaviour scale (61.90), meaning that they have poor moral behaviour on the average. The mean score of use of social media (75.12) falls below the established norm of 61.90. This suggests

that, on average, the participants' exhibit lower moral behavior. Conversely, their mean score for use of social media is 75.12, which surpasses the normative value of 62.94, indicating a high level of social media engagement among the students. The average age of the participants is 18.84

years. For the correlations of the variables, moral behavior of the respondents demonstrated a significant negative correlation with use of social media ($r = -$

0.214, $p < 0.01$), but failed to significantly correlate with age ($r = -0.025$, $p > 0.05$). Age did not correlate with any of the variables.

Table 2: Multiple Regression of Use of Social Media, Age and Moral Behaviour among Undergraduate Teenagers.

Model	B	t value	p value	Decision
Use of Social Media	-.214	-4.397	.000	Sig.
Age	-.027	-.557	-.578	N.S.
R ²	.046			
F	9.798			
Df	2,403			

Criterion variable: Moral Behaviour

Table 2 presents the results of the hypothesis testing. The first hypothesis, which posited that use of social media would not significantly predict the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates, was rejected ($\beta = -0.214$, $p < 0.01$, $t = -4.397$). This indicates that use of social media is a significant predictor of moral behavior. The negative relationship suggests that as use of social media increases, moral behavior tends to decline, and vice versa.

The second hypothesis, which stated that the teenage undergraduates' age will not significantly predict moral behavior, was accepted. The R-squared value of .046 indicates that use of social media and age together account for 4.6% of the variation in moral behavior. The entire model was statistically significant [$df (2,403) = 9.798$, $p < 0.01$], demonstrating that use of social media and age collectively influence the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Presenting Mean and Standard Deviation Differences in Moral Behaviour

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
1. Female	59.63	7.32	199
2. Male	59.73	7.46	206

Note: N- Number

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation scores for the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates. The results indicate no significant difference between female

undergraduates (M = 59.63, SD = 7.34) and male undergraduates (M = 59.73, SD = 7.46) in their moral behavior.

Table 4: One-Way ANOVA Summary Result of Gender Differences on Moral Behaviour

Source	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.113	1	1.113	.020	.887
Within Groups	22006.798	403	54.607		
Total	22006.798	404			

The third hypothesis proposed that male and female teenage undergraduates will not significantly differ on their moral behaviour. This hypothesis was supported [F (1,403) = 0.020, p = 0.887], indicating that gender does not have a significant impact on the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates (Table 4).

Summary of Results

The findings from this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Use of social media significantly and negatively predicts moral behavior of teenage undergraduates.
2. Teenage undergraduates' age does not significantly predict moral behavior.
3. Male and female teenage undergraduates' has no significant difference in moral behavior.

Discussion

There is high prevalence of use of social media among teenage undergraduates in Imo State, often bordering on addiction. It underscores the

increasing moral decline among this demographic, attributing it in part to excessive social media engagement. The findings suggest that social media addiction contributes to a growing disregard for morality in Nigerian society. Furthermore, the results indicate that while social media significantly influences the moral behavior of teenagers, age and gender do not play a significant role in this relationship.

The first hypothesis which posits that use of social media will not significantly predict the moral behavior of teenage undergraduates is rejected. Social media negatively predicted moral behaviour among teenage undergraduates in Imo State. This means the more teenage undergraduates engage social media, the lower (poorer) the moral behaviour. As supported by Oloyede *et al* (2022) that social media contributes in creation of awareness and promotion of patterns of low morality and morality deterioration in the society. This saying "What you do in secret guides your reality" manifests here as the users of social media are engaging in some heinous activities with the apps but being revealed in their posts, contents shared and liked. Otubue and Oji (2024) confirm that students use social media apps for sex appeals from public. Social media being a world of its own has many groups and influences that direct behaviours. As people learn good behaviours, they are equally influenced to learn bad morals.

In contrast to the first finding, the second hypothesis which states that the teenage undergraduates' age will not significantly predict the moral behavior, is accepted. This

implies that age does have a significant relationship with moral behaviour. This finding is supported by Hertz and Krettenauer (2016), who showed that youth exhibit an increased pattern of morality compared to older adults. Similarly, Lu and Fung (2019) found that older adults are more likely to view moral behaviour negatively than younger individuals.

Teenagers, still within their developmental stage, have several years before their brains fully mature in adulthood. The prefrontal cortex, located behind the forehead, is one of the last parts of the brain to mature. The area is responsible for decision-making, planning, and prioritizing behaviour. Consequently, teenagers face challenges in these areas and can be easily influenced by social media content, leading to immoral behaviours. Ismail (2023) demonstrated this by showing that all adolescent students in the study exhibited low moral issues.

Similarly, the third hypothesis which states that male and female undergraduates will not significantly differ in moral behavior is accepted. This shows that both genders are same in the low level of morality. Muhammed-Lawal and Salahu-Deen (2021) study supported this as they found out that both male and female gender were related same on the moral behaviour status. Though immorality can be group or culturally determined, the acts of immorality are seen in both gender. It is not gender based.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research will help primary care givers; parents, guidance and university administration in realizing the degree of immorality social

media can cause to the adolescent undergraduate wards. As it was identified that teenagers are still experiencing development and maturation, hence the call for serious control of social media use especially by youths as it leads to many ominous acts. The results showed a positive relationship between social media contents and challenges experiences by teenage undergraduates. It recommends

Support to the moderation of social media use by government.

That social media use should be involved in the orientation program and courses in schools, addressing dangers of morality and poor academic achievements among students.

The National Universities Commission (NUC) should integrate awareness of social media misuse and its consequences into the Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS). With universities having the flexibility to tailor 30% of their curriculum to local needs, this measure would help mitigate academic distractions, online fraud, and inappropriate online behavior among teenagers.

Suggestion for further studies includes

Future research should incorporate additional psychological assessment tools to provide deeper insights into the relationship between social media use and psychophysiological factors.

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